

SCOPING FOR RISK

Risk assessment for enhanced efficiency and transparency in Integrated Ecosystem Assessment Scoping Step

DESCRIPTION

MISSION ATLANTIC is the first project to adapt and apply an established risk assessment methodology as the first ‘scoping’ step in an Integrated Ecosystem Assessment (IEA), integrating it with stakeholder engagement and question specification/scenario identification to operationalise the “SCOPING” part of the IEA Cycle in a standardised and transparent way. The process has been developed in parallel with the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), and has since been adopted into their technical guidelines for producing the ICES Ecosystem Overviews, key ecosystem advice products. The approach is now used and applied by the ICES IEA groups and associated workshops during the production of Ecosystem Overviews. This process has improved operationality, comparability, transparency and consistency, whilst also demonstrating how Mission Atlantic outputs have contributed to establishing best practice in the field.

The analyses were carried out in the R statistical environment and are publicly available at: github.com/Missionatlantic/MissionAtlantic-RISK-Analysis

FACTS AT A GLANCE

WP1 AND CELTIC SEA CASE STUDY LEAD

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INSTITUTES

KEYWORDS

Integrated Ecosystem Assessment
 Ecosystem-based Management
 Risk Assessment
 Scoping
 Impact Risk

LINKS TO RELATED PROJECTS

MISSION ATLANTIC
<https://missionatlantic.eu>

LINKS TO RELATED WORK

ICES Ecosystem Approaches and Methods Steering Group (EAMSG)
www.ices.dk/community/groups/Pages/EAMSG.aspx
 NOAA IEA Program:
www.integratedecosystemassessment.noaa.gov/

REFERENCE*

Pedreschi D et al (2023) Operationalising ODEMM risk assessment for Integrated Ecosystem Assessment scoping: Complexity vs. manageability. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9:1037878. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2022.1037878

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL

TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment

Human activities create pressures that affect multiple parts of the ecosystem. To be comprehensive and holistic, all human activities/sectors, all the pressures they create, and all parts of the ecosystem should be considered. In practice, limitations in data, knowledge, time, and capacity require us to ‘triage’ the relevant elements in order to flag areas of concern/highest risk for more in-depth analyses during subsequent IEA steps. Ecological risk assessments allow us to do this, but methods often face challenges in terms of adaptability, scalability, ease of use, ability to incorporate different levels/types of knowledge and data, ultimately limiting their uptake in management and advice.

Informed by stakeholder and user feedback, existing risk assessment approaches were reviewed and critically evaluated, ultimately resulting in a simplified, streamlined, operational, and fit-for-purpose adapted approach that can readily be used by capacity-limited scientists, researchers and managers. A hybrid analytical approach combining the relative contribution of each individual component (i.e., sector, pressure) and the top individual pressure pathways was used to produce a more informative output that details the top 5 sectors and pressures relevant to a given region. Outputs were ground-truthed with both stakeholder groups and expert panels and found to better reflect their understanding of the system than the original approaches and metrics.

The adapted risk assessment approach has improved uptake and application in practice, helping to progress IEA as a tool for Ecosystem-based Management. The approach has been used by all eight Mission Atlantic case studies, and is used by ICES in their Ecosystem Overview advisory products. Further potential users include researchers, IEA practitioners, managers and decision-makers.

BACKGROUND

The MISSION ATLANTIC project seeks to progress ecosystem-based management through the application of Integrated Ecosystem Assessments (IEAs) at basin and regional scales. In doing so, the project identifies the ecosystem components most at risk from natural hazards and the consequences of human activities and prioritizes efforts while seeking to identify trade-offs and inform decision-making.

		% relative contribution	
		Top linkages	Entire Assessment
Sectors	Fishing	57.6	77.5
	Land-based Industry	4.4	4.4
	Waste Water	4.3	4.3
	Shipping	3.3	3.3
	Tourism/Recreation	2.7	2.7
	Total	58	92
Pressures	Bycatch	23.1	24.1
	Species Extraction	18.9	20.1
	Incidental Loss	7.9	14.0
	Litter	12.9	12.9
	Abrasion	7.9	9.7
Total	58	81	

Relative contribution scores for the top linkage chains and entire assessment for the MISSION ATLANTIC Celtic Sea Case Study area*

Linkage diagram illustrating the top sectors, pressures, and linkage chains, as presented in the ICES Celtic Seas Ecosystem Overview (ICES 2024).

APPLICATION

“[...] The] hybrid assessment, based on both IR and relative contributions, provides a risk assessment that meets the scoping needs of IEA by providing a high level and comprehensive approach, enabling the assessment of all relevant sectors and pressures, and identification of those that present the most urgent foci for management action. Furthermore, this presents a common approach to enable comparisons between ecoregions and/or case study areas. Critically for ICES IEA groups, it provides a documented method through which they can carry out a more detailed scoping exercise for IEA, and summarizes those assessment elements to the level of detail required for the Ecosystem Overviews via a hierarchical approach. In this way, the exercise can serve two purposes, thus saving on group time and energy.” (*Pedreschi D et al, 2023)

RELATION TO MISSION ‘RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS’: The risk assessment process enables a comprehensive, holistic and integrative assessment and prioritisation of all of the pressures and impacts (including pollution: Mission Objective 2), affecting marine ecosystems and biodiversity, a critical step to enable restoration and protection of systems (Mission Objective 1). The assessment incorporates all sectors and activities that create impacts or pressures which may affect our ability to deliver on the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy (Mission Objective 3).